

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“CAMIGUIN: PROGRESS NEVER STOPS”

Progress never stops is a phrase that refers to the ongoing growth, improvement, and development whether in technology, individual lives, or society in its entirety. It's a concept that means there is always room where we can learn more, build better relationships to one another, and become a better individual to others. It's what drives individuals forward, to always evolve, to always learn, and to always strive. In short, progress never stops is a continuous journey of growth, improvement, and development.

In Camiguin, the phrase “Progress Never Stops” is also used to describe the growth, improvement, and development of its infrastructures that makes the lives of its constituents better. Farm-to-market roads, for example, makes the delivery of the farmer's produce like vegetables, fruits, and meat products to nearby municipal markets or barangay markets with less hassle and less labor. Farmers can save their hard-earned money by hiring less laborers to carry their produce. Further, farms located in the mountain areas of the island is more accessible now than what it was before. With farm-to-market roads, the lives of our farmers, who are constituents of the island, have become better and the relationships between farmers and the consumers of their produce have become better also.

Another example is the Cong. PPR Sports Complex, particularly the oval track where runners, joggers, and those who just wants to stay healthy by walking, be safe during their exercises. I am one of these oval track users, and I can really say, base on my experience, that exercises like running, jogging, and walking done inside the sports complex is safer than doing it in the road. You can even bring your kids in the oval track without overthinking on their safety. No vehicles to always watch for coming your way or coming behind you. Listening to music thru your headset to enjoy while exercising is doable too, and you're completely safe for any vehicular accidents.

We also have the airport and the seaports. These ports make the life of every resident of the island better in terms of their livelihood because of the island's tourism industry. These ports serve as the entry point for tourists to come and visit Camiguin island. Better tourism industry, better economy in the island. This is evident during the annual event of Lanzones Festival every October, Christmas breaks, summer vacations, and Holy Week. People from all walks of life visit the island mostly for a way out of their daily lives, for experience, and for some spontaneity.

Farm-to-market roads, sports complex, airport, and seaports are just a few of the infrastructures on Camiguin island that make the life of its constituents better. There are others but there are many to mention. I'm just mentioning four of them because of my first-hand experience.

All of these have become possible because of one man who have a vision for his beloved island, the late **Congressman Pedro Palarca Romualdo**. His vision is continued by his sons and grandsons, Cong. Jurdin Jesus M. Romualdo, Vice Gov. Rodin M. Romualdo, Gov. Xavier Jesus D. Romualdo, Mayor Yñigo Jesus D. Romualdo, and Brgy. Capt. Peter Dann C. Romualdo.

